

The Concept of Linguocultural Competence, Its Socio-Pedagogical Relevance and Necessity

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Abstract: The purpose of this article is to analyze different points of view on communicative competence and its types described in local and foreign literature, to justify the need to distinguish linguocultural competence, to analyze its importance and role in intensive foreign language teaching.

Keywords: foreign language, linguistic competence, communication, native language, communicative competence.

Introduction

It is known that the purpose of teaching a foreign language is to teach students to communicate in a foreign language, which is carried out in all types of speech activity, to achieve a full understanding of this concept in the formation of their communicative competence. "In essence, the task of teaching a foreign language in the conditions of intensive training is focused on the formation of students' speech ability, communicative competence in real life communication".

The term "competence" comes from the Latin word *Competere*, which means "to be able to do something." This term was introduced by N. Chomsky with reference to W. Humboldt in connection with the study of the tasks of generative grammar. Initially, it referred to the ability necessary to perform certain linguistic actions in the native language (Chomsky, 1965).

After analysing a number of works devoted to this problem, we came to the conclusion that there is still no single definition of the term "communicative competence", since representatives of different fields of knowledge approach the description of this concept from their own point of view. Some researchers believe that the goal of education is communicative competence (I.A. Zimnyaya, G.V. Kolshansky, L.L. Fedorova, D. Vake, K.D. Banning, Finocchio, D.K. Kochan, K.E. Piefo, Savignon, Z. Ulrich). Other authors highlight linguistic and communicative competence as the goal of education (E.M. Vereshchagin, M.N. Vyatutnev, V.G. Kostomarov, etc.).

According to many methodologists, communicative competence is a complex multi-component formation that includes various elements, such as: linguistic, sociolinguistic, paralinguistic, subject, etc. (V.A. Gorina, L.A. Ermakova, V.A. Kokkota, E. L. Korchagina, G. N. Loginova, T. A. L. Tretyakova. Fedorova, L. Bachman, M. Kanale, R. Cooper, H. Helmikh, H. Melenk, A. Palmer, M. Swain, etc.).

There are also researchers who consider individual components of communicative

competence as independent one. (T.I. Kapitonova, I.I. Leyfa, A.N. Shchukina, Z. Ulrich, etc.).

The term "communicative competence" appeared in foreign methodological literature a long time ago and has been significantly revised over the years (in the works of L. Bachman, B. Badura, N. Ditmar, J. Gumperz, J. Habermas, D. Hymes, A. Palmer, etc.). D. Hymes was one of the first who clearly showed that knowledge of the language implies not only knowledge of grammar and vocabulary, but also the social conditions of their use (Hymes 1967: 8-28). Although the importance of extralinguistic knowledge for the formation of communicative competence has been recognized by many methodological scientists, for a long period of time the dependence of the processes of production and reception of speech information on socio-cultural factors has not been actively studied. For the first time, this connection was thoroughly studied in the works of F. Erikson and J. Schultz (1982). Meanwhile, J. Gumperz gave a new definition of communicative competence: "This is the knowledge and observance of certain norms of communication in order to attract the attention of the interlocutor, understand and continue the conversation" (Sitregg 1984): 278).

Nowadays in Western pedagogy, communicative competence is understood as the student's ability to communicate adequately in specific communicative situations and the ability to organize oral communication, taking into account the socio-cultural norms of speech and the communicative purpose of the statement (Bunting, Kochan 1973): 163; Gunthner 1989: 437-447). According to many methodologists in Western Europe (for example, Germany), The formation of communicative competence is the goal of teaching a foreign language.

With the development of the concepts of intercultural education, many foreign methodologists prefer to expand the concept of "communication" and distinguish between "intercultural communicative competence" (Bayram 1989: 5) or "communicative competence in intercultural communication" (Muller 1994: 97). The well-known scientist I.A. Zimnyaya also considered communicative competence as the goal of education, although it is very distant and cannot be achieved during the training period. At the same time, she interprets communicative competence as the result and goal of learning. Communicative competence, according to I.A. Zimnyaya, is "the formed ability of a person to act as a subject of communicative activity of communication" (Zimnyaya 1989: 27). In conclusion, I.A. Zimnyaya considers communicative competence as an ability that can only be formed, developed and diagnosed. (Zimnyaya 1989: 29).

M.N. Vyatutnev identifies two types of competences: linguistic and communicative. He gives the following definition of linguistic competence: "Linguacultural competence is the intuitive knowledge of a small number of rules that underlie the construction of the deep structures of the language, which are transformed into various statements in the process of communication" (Vyatutnev 1975: 55-64). But at the same time, he emphasizes that linguacultural competence is only one stage in the process of language acquisition. In the interpretation of A.A. Leontiev the concept of language competence or language ability is defined as a specific psychophysiological mechanism that forms an element of a three-term opposition - "language ability - language process - language standard". (A.A. Leontiev 1970:132).

Under communicative competence, M.N. Vyatutnev understands the ability to select and implement programs of speech actions in communication, depending on the ability of a person to act in the environment; the ability to classify situations depending on the topic, tasks, communicative relations that arise between the participants before the conversation, as well as during the adaptation process; regional knowledge. A few years later, the author identifies three levels of communicative competence - initial, intermediate and advanced.

He emphasizes that the level of communicative competence in the native language is different for different people, that among native speakers there is no people with the same communicative competence, so their social and communicative activity is not the same.

"Starting from elementary competence at an early age, a person passes through intermediate competences in his development, and in adulthood he develops stable communicative competence of the language, but with individual characteristics inherent in each person" (Vyatutnev 1983: 124). M.N. Vyatutnev notes that these differences can be very significant for a native speaker in all four types of speech activity, therefore, in his opinion, it is appropriate to talk not about one communicative competence, but also a combination of four skills: writing, listening, reading and speaking. However, this point of view does not correspond to the general idea of a single speech mechanism and, in our opinion, has the right to exist only for methodological purposes, taking into account the conditionality of such a distinction.

E.M. Vereshchagin and V.G. Kostomarov also distinguish between linguistic and communicative competences. By linguacultural competence they understand the speaker's ability to create a grammatically correct chain of phrases based on the rules taught to him (even regardless of their content), and by communicative competence - a set of social, national-cultural rules. (Vereshchagin, Kostomarov 1982).

The views of another group of Methodists on communicative competence as a complex system of interconnected components are undoubtedly of interest, for example, linguistic, paralinguistic, etc., the possession of which indicates that the individual has knowledge, skills and qualifications in the field of language, including in the subfield of specialization, as well as in the studied specialty and regionalism. (Ermakova, 1988; Tretyakova 1991, Fedorova 1980).

Some researchers went further by distinguishing the individual components of communicative competence into independent types (T. I. Kapitonova and A. N. Shchukin 1987, V. A. Kokkota 1989, I. I. Leif 1995 L. Bachman and A. Palmer 1986, M. Canale and M. Swain, Z. Swain).

At the same time, the purpose of learning competence "... it means knowledge, skills, skills formed in the process of teaching a certain subject, as well as the ability to carry out any activity" (Kapitonova, Shchukin). 1987: 216). The authors identify four types of competencies, e1) linguistic competence, which is knowledge of the language system; 2) communicative competence or skills that allow you to communicate in a language; 3) methodological competence inherent in future language teachers; and 4) regional competence or knowledge of the country of the language being studied (Kapitonova, Shchukin 1987:70).

This approach is also fixed in some programs of higher educational institutions, in which the formation of linguistic, communicative, regional and communicative-methodological competence of students is put forward as a practical learning goal.

Understanding the conditionality and limitations of such a distribution of types of competencies, we nevertheless believe that in the interests of our research, such an approach deserves attention. It can be noted that the achievement of practical, educational, educational and developmental goals in the training of future teachers can be achieved only through the formation of several types of competencies: communicative, linguistic and linguistic socio-cultural, as well as professional psychological and pedagogical competence in a certain discipline. These types of competencies are interrelated and arranged in a certain hierarchy, which can be represented systematically .

The most important competence is a communicative competence, in the methodology which means the ability to choose and implement programs of speech behavior in a foreign language, depending on the goals and content of communication. It is also necessary to organize this communication taking into account the relationships of people and communicative attitudes, having a communicative strategy and tactics. The basis for the

formation of communicative competence is language, which can be defined as the ability to understand and produce correct statements of various levels and volumes based on the knowledge gained about the language system and its functional types of speech.

Considering the professional orientation of teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic higher educational institutions, it should be noted that the level of development of a student's communicative competence is indirectly related to the subject-professional (possession of an integrated system). Knowledge in the professional field, the general culture of a specialist, his professional way of thinking) and psychological and pedagogical competence are important. The didactics refers to the abilities and skills of a teacher based on knowledge in the field of didactics, psychology, methods and necessary for the implementation of his professional activities. Finally, the last type of competence that is the object of our research is linguistic and cultural. Together with language competence, it is the basis for the formation of communicative competence. On the one hand, it partially mediates subject-professional and psychological-pedagogical competence, while on the other hand, it mediates to a large extent through linguistic competence.

In this study, we propose a working definition of the currently generally accepted scientific definition of the linguistic competence: 1) the ability of this individual to carry out cross-cultural communication based on knowledge of lexical units with national-cultural semantics and the ability to apply them; 2) having socio-cultural conditional scenarios and patterns of national specific behavior using communicative techniques ; 3) the ability to use basic knowledge (historical-cultural, socio-cultural and ethno-cultural background) to achieve cultural understanding with native speakers.

Between all types of competence, researchers highlight the particular importance and role of the training of future teachers in achieving practical, educational, general and Development Goals. The importance of linguacultural competence comes from its functions, and the main ones are:

- *value-oriented*: given that any training is aimed at the social nature of the content of the goals, it is necessary to take into account that the result of the formation of the LC should be the student's ability to participate in intercultural communication; forms a connection between two (or several) cultures, assimilates the positive experience of foreign and native cultures.
- *cognitive*, which manifests the acceptance of other folk culture and direct access to its values, in the elimination of stereotypes and prejudices and in the formation of a positive attitude towards the native language, as well as in the acquisition of wealth stored in the learning language;
- *Stimulating function*: it is known that regional research and socio-cultural materials, on the basis of which the LC is formed, stimulated and increase interest in science and the educational process;
- *Regulatory function*: it provides an adequate understanding of the of native speaker's speech , its linguistic-cultural concept and the correct form and content of the student's own statements, "cultural shock", that is, ultimately, the mutual adequate understanding of the participants of the communicative act belonging to different national cultures.

Conclusion

Generally researchers considered and analyzed various points of views of researchers on the nature of communicative competence and its types and came to the conclusion that in order to solve the problems of our research, it is advisable to single out the formation of LC. Along with communicative, linguistic or subject-professional and psychological-pedagogical competence, it allows achieving the ultimate goals of education in higher

educational institutions. Performing its most important functions, LC plays an important role in the professional training of future teachers, because It carries a great humanitarian burden. Moreover, its formation is relevant not only for a foreign language teacher, but also for other disciplines, since every modern teacher should be familiar with many cultures of the peoples of the world and be formed as an integral cultural and linguistic personality. By forming LC among students of non-linguistic higher educational institutions through a foreign language, we increase their personal potential.

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